

OPTIMAL DESIGN OF VARIABLE THICKNESS COMPOSITE STRUCTURES MADE BY PATCHES USING STACKING SEQUENCE TABLES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an optimization methodology combining thickness and stacking sequence optimization within a bi-level optimization framework. The first level optimization is a classical lamination parameters and thickness continuous optimization. The second level combines Stacking Sequence Table (SST) optimization for laminate blending using a specialized evolutionary algorithm and continuous thickness optimization in an innovative way. A SST describes a unique laminate for each number of plies between a lower and an upper bound. Thus, a SST describes a relation between the laminate thickness and its homogenised stiffness. This relation is used to link the thickness to the shell stiffness within a continuous thickness optimization. The method is applied to the mass minimization of an automotive thermoplastic composite wishbone under displacement and strength constraints with a significant final mass saving compared to the reference uniform thickness solution.

1 INTRODUCTION

Manufacturing large panels with thickness variations obtained by adding or terminating plies within the structure is nowadays a common practice in the aeronautical industry. Detailed design of such structures is usually based on the subdivision of the global problem into local panel design problems. The mass of the structure can be minimized by tailoring the thickness and lay-ups of each panel to the load distribution. Continuity of the plies has to be preserved in order to obtain one-shot manufacturable structures and avoid stacking sequence mismatch between adjacent panels. The design of laminated structures with ply-drops is commonly referred to as blending. Various methods have been published for laminate blending optimization. In particular, Irisarri *et al.* [1] introduced the notion of Stacking Sequence Table (SST) as a convenient representation of the solutions to solve laminate blending optimization problems.

Fast manufacturing processes based on patches of reduced dimensions for smaller structures are currently receiving a growing attention from designers from both the automotive industry and aerospace equipment manufacturers. This work addresses the corresponding lightweight design problem and proposes an original method based on the use of SST within a bi-level optimization framework. Section 2 presents the overall optimization strategy. The first level optimization is described in Section 3 where continuous optimization is used to find an idealized design. Section 4 details the second level optimization. A stiffness matching phase is used to find promising SSTs and initialize an optimization of the thickness of the structure in which the relation between the thickness variation and the stiffness variation of the shell is parameterized by the SSTs. The method is applied in Section 5 to the mass minimization of an automotive thermoplastic composite wishbone under displacement and strength constraints.

2 GLOBAL OPTIMIZATION STRATEGY

The global optimization strategy is based on a bi-level decomposition of the problem. The first level of the decomposition consists in searching for the optimal thickness and stiffness of the laminate using a homogenized shell model of the laminates. The second level consists in searching for the corresponding optimal stacking-sequence. Various implementations of the bi-level optimization strategy for composite laminates can be found in the literature [2–6]. These implementations mainly differ in the degree of sophistication of the optimization algorithms used for the first level and second level optimizations, and in the way the two steps are related. The first level optimization results in an idealized design that corresponds to an upper bound of the mechanical performances of the structures. Indeed, the homogenized shell representation of the laminates makes it difficult to enforce manufacturing constraints into the optimization. Additionally, the feasible design domain of laminate macroscopic stiffness is difficult to describe with accuracy, especially for coupled problems [7–9]. The overall efficiency of the bi-level scheme depends on the way the first level idealized optimum is targeted at the second level. Aiming to match the stiffness distribution of the discrete design to the stiffness distribution of the idealized design is very efficient in terms of computational cost since no structural analysis is required. The main drawback of the method, however, is that without a structural analysis, the feasibility of the design is not guaranteed. As an alternative approach to stiffness matching, performance matching is proposed and implemented in [3,10]. At the second level, an evolutionary algorithm is applied to a multi-point structural approximation built with a modified Shepard's interpolation method in stiffness space. The method allows a broader exploration of the discrete design space than stiffness-matching and returns feasible designs, while the number of required structural analyses is kept very low.

3 CONTINUOUS STIFFNESS AND THICKNESS OPTIMIZATION

In the present work, the first level optimization is performed using the method of feasible directions implemented in Altair® OptiStruct®. The method presented in this paper is intended for mass minimization of a composite structure under buckling, displacement and local strength constraints. In the following, the structure to be optimized is divided into zones. Each zone corresponds to a single thickness and laminate. The subdivision of the structure into zones is not subject to change during the optimization.

3.1 Lamination parameters and thickness optimization

At first level optimization, the design variables are the total thickness and the lamination parameters in each region of the structure. The laminates are assumed uncoupled so that eight lamination parameters only are required to fully describe the membrane stiffness matrix \mathbf{A} and the bending stiffness matrix \mathbf{D} of the classical lamination theory [11], regardless of the number of plies:

$$\mathbf{A} = h(\mathbf{\Gamma}_0 + V_1\mathbf{\Gamma}_1 + V_2\mathbf{\Gamma}_2 + V_3\mathbf{\Gamma}_3 + V_4\mathbf{\Gamma}_4) \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{D} = \frac{h^3}{12}(\mathbf{\Gamma}_0 + W_1\mathbf{\Gamma}_1 + W_2\mathbf{\Gamma}_2 + W_3\mathbf{\Gamma}_3 + W_4\mathbf{\Gamma}_4) \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{\Gamma}_{i=1,\dots,4}$ matrices are defined by the elastic properties of the base ply and $V_{i=1,\dots,4}$ and $W_{i=1,\dots,4}$ are the lamination parameters and h is the total thickness of the laminate. In the following, the material of the ply is a fixed parameter of the optimization. There are nine design variables per region in the structure $(h, V_{i=1,\dots,4}, W_{i=1,\dots,4})$. The use of lamination parameters as design variables for continuous optimization of composite structures has been thoroughly discussed in the literature [12,13]. All lamination parameters are bounded between -1 and 1. In this study, we use the inequalities introduced by Raju *et al.* [14] to limit the feasible region in the design space.

3.2 Strength constraint

Incorporating failure criteria into the lamination parameter design space is a difficult task since the stacking sequence is not known at the first optimization level. Using the Tsai-Wu failure criterion, a minimal failure envelope is derived in [15] that guarantees a failure free region of the lamination parameter space regardless of the ply orientations in the laminate stacking sequence. An alternative method based on the polar method is proposed in [16]. In the present work, the minimal failure envelope of a modified Tsai-Hill failure criterion is computed by enumeration of the 16-ply symmetrical laminates with ply orientations restricted to steps of 15°. All laminates satisfy the 10% guideline, as formulated in stiffness space in [17]. The minimal failure envelope is then approximated by an ellipsoid evaluated on the macroscopic in-plane stresses. To account for bending, the failure criterion is evaluated on both the outer and inner surface of the shells.

4 STACKING SEQUENCE TABLES RETRIEVING

The aim of the second level optimization is to retrieve for each zone a stacking sequence and number of plies. In particular, structural continuity between adjacent zones has to be enforced to ensure the integrity of the structure. Here, continuity is enforced through the use of Stacking Sequence Tables (SST). A SST describes a unique laminate for each number of plies between a lower and an upper bound. The SST is built by adding plies one by one from the thinner laminate to the thicker one. Fig. 1 illustrates the concept of stacking sequence table.

Figure 1: Thickness transition zone (right) and view of the corresponding SST (left).

In this work, the second level optimization is divided into three distinct phases. The first phase is a stiffness matching optimization with fixed thickness distribution. The second phase aims at finding feasible designs allowing small thickness variations around the thickness distribution of the first level idealized design. The third phase consists in rounding the thickness distribution to an integer number of plies and switch from the homogenized representation to a layer-by-layer representation of the laminates.

4.1 Stiffness matching using stacking sequence tables

The optimization is performed using a modified version of the evolutionary algorithm for stacking sequence tables developed by Irisarri *et al.* [1] and extended in [10] for multiple SSTs. The algorithm is implemented in Matlab®. The algorithm is modified to keep the distribution of number of plies unchanged. The distribution of number of plies corresponds to the thickness distribution of the first level idealized design, rounded to the nearest greater integer number of plies.

Proximity of two stiffness distributions ($\mathbf{A}_1, \mathbf{D}_1$) and ($\mathbf{A}_2, \mathbf{D}_2$) is evaluated based on the distance in stiffness space proposed in [3]. Here, a bi-objective optimization is performed that aims at minimizing the \mathbf{A} -distance in membrane stiffness space and the \mathbf{D} -distance in bending stiffness space, respectively defined in Eq. 3 and Eq. 4 where the operator \cdot stands for the dot product, i.e., the trace of the product of two square matrices. The distances are computed for each region of the structure and aggregated

through a weighted sum of the zone-to-zone distances. The weight of each zone corresponds to its surface, divided by the total surface of the structure.

$$d(\mathbf{A}_1, \mathbf{A}_2) = \mathbf{A}_1^{-1} : \mathbf{A}_2 + \mathbf{A}_1 : \mathbf{A}_2^{-1} - 6 \quad (3)$$

$$d(\mathbf{D}_1, \mathbf{D}_2) = \mathbf{D}_1^{-1} : \mathbf{D}_2 + \mathbf{D}_1 : \mathbf{D}_2^{-1} - 6 \quad (4)$$

The algorithm performs a Pareto multiobjective optimization. The optimization returns a set of non-dominated solutions as close to the true Pareto front of the problem as possible and evenly distributed along this front. Each solution represents a trade-off between the objectives. The stiffness matching phase returns a set of designs whose number of plies and laminates are known in each zone. Structural integrity of the design is obtained through the use of the SST-based blending method. However, feasibility of the designs with respect to the mechanical specifications of the overall design problem is not guaranteed.

4.2 SST-based thickness optimization

The SST defines a relation between the terms of the stiffness matrices of the classical lamination theory and the local number of plies in the structure. This relation can be easily extended to continuous thickness variations. Fig. 2 shows the evolutions of the membrane and bending stiffness as functions of the laminate thickness parameterized by the SST presented in Fig. 1. These functions can be interpolated to link the thickness to the material properties of the shell within a continuous optimization.

Figure 2: Evolution of the membrane and bending stiffness defined by a SST.

In the present work, a continuous thickness optimization is performed using Altair® OptiStruct® for each non-dominated design issued from the stiffness matching phase. The objective of the optimization is to minimize the mass of the structure while ensuring feasibility of the design. The variables are the thickness of the zones of the structure. The allowed thickness variation corresponds to the addition or removal of one ply with respect to the thickness distribution used for the stiffness matching phase. On that reduced variation range, linear approximations of the functions parameterized by the SST and relating the shell stiffness to the thickness are implemented.

4.3 Final post-processing

In the post processing of the optimization, the thickness distributions are rounded up to integer number of plies and the final design is translated from PSHELL to PCOMP elements. Failure of the material can be checked at ply-level using the modified Tsai-Hill first-ply failure criterion rather than its approximation (see § 3.2).

5 RESULTS

The method is applied to the mass minimization of an automotive thermoplastic composite wishbone. The optimization results are compared to the reference design developed and manufactured by PSA, CETIM and Onera [18]. The part is composed of two symmetrical shells with a uniform lay-up of theoretical thickness 3.3 mm (see Fig. 3). An innovative manufacturing process was developed at CETIM to thermoform and weld the two shells in the same tool. The stacking sequence of the reference design is [0/45/0/45/0/45/0/45/0/45/0]. The part is manufactured from a balanced woven thermoplastic ply. For the initial design, material properties in warp (0°) and weft (90°) directions were assumed to be close enough so that 0° and 90° directions on one hand, and -45° and +45° directions on the other hand could not be differentiated. In the present work, the values of the elastic properties and strengths are based on subsequent material characterization tests performed at Onera [19]. The material strengths in warp and weft direction are significantly different, thus ply orientation angles ranging from -75° to 90° by steps of 15° are considered.

The part is divided into 35 zones based on engineering judgment (see Fig. 3). The optimization aims at finding a blended solution that minimizes the mass of the part. Due to process constraints, the minimal thickness is set to 1.8 mm (6 plies) and the maximal thickness to 4.2 mm (14 plies). After analysis of the mechanical specification, the optimization constraints are limited to a single critical load case for which the material must not fail and the displacement of point D (see Fig. 3) must remain within the following limits: $0 \leq u_x \leq 9$ mm and -0.7 mm $\leq u_y \leq 0$. Failure of the material is evaluated at all elements of the structure using the modified Tsai-Hill failure criterion in post-processing of an elastic stress analysis (see § 3.2). The geometry of the part ensures significant margin with regard to global buckling, thus only half the part is modeled. The mass of a single shell of the reference design is $m_0 = 434$ g. Within the prescribed thickness boundary values, the mass of the shell can vary from $m_{min} = 236$ g to $m_{max} = 552$ g.

Figure 3: View of the reference design [18] presented at JEC Europe 2013 along with the mesh, zoning, boundary conditions and loading used for the optimization model.

5.1 First-level optimization

Fig. 4 shows the convergence of the optimization starting from four different initial designs in terms of lamination parameters. All starting points share the uniform 3.3 mm thickness distribution of the reference design. It is clear from the figure that depending on the starting point, the first optimization run converges to different local optima. Analysis of the iterations of the optimization runs show that the design subspace corresponding to the lamination parameters is poorly used. Indeed, the mass of the structure depends on the thickness distribution only. The distribution of material anisotropy affects the optimization constraints only. In order to escape from the local optima, a second optimization run is chained to the first one. The thickness distribution is fixed and set to the output of the first optimization run. The objective is to minimize the maximal constraint by optimizing the distribution of material anisotropy. The minmax optimization creates a margin with respect to the active constraints that can be used subsequently to obtain further mass reduction by iterating on the process. Fig. 4 shows that in the present case, the proposed optimization scheme seems to converge quickly to similar designs regardless of the initial points.

Figure 4: Convergence of the first level optimization with four different initial designs.

It can be seen in Fig. 4 that the reference design is the only feasible initial design with respect to the optimization constraints. Consequently, convergence of the optimization is much faster when using the reference design as initial point. The lightest solution found weights about $m = 330$ g. The first level idealized design defines the upper bound of the potential mass saving which is 24% in the present case. Fig. 5 shows the corresponding thickness distribution and the polar plots of the stiffness $E_{11}(\theta)$ for all zones. Strength and displacement constraints are active for this design.

Figure 5: Thickness distribution of the idealized design and polar plots of the stiffness $E_{11}(\theta)$.

5.2 Second-level optimization

The distribution of thickness of the first level idealized design is rounded up to the nearest greater integer number of plies. The distribution of number of plies is fixed. The purpose of the optimization is to match the stiffness distribution defined by the SSTs and the stiffness distribution of the first level idealized design. Fig. 6 presents the results of the stiffness matching phase. Each point in the figure corresponds to the distance of a SST to the target stiffness distribution corresponding to the first level idealized design. Both distances between membrane stiffness distributions (A -distance) and bending stiffness distributions (D -distance) are minimized with a Pareto multiobjective approach. Three SSTs are shown in the figure, corresponding to the minimal A -distance, the minimal sum of the two distances and minimal D -distance respectively. All laminates satisfy the 10% design guideline and the symmetry guideline. The covering plies on the surfaces of the laminates are not dropped within the SSTs.

Figure 6: Results of the stiffness matching phase.

The SSTs obtained after the stiffness matching phase are further optimized to ensure that the failure and maximal displacement constraints are satisfied. The optimization variables are the thicknesses of the zones of the structure. Each SST parameterize a relation between the shell stiffness and the shell thickness (see § 4.2). Linear approximations of these relations are implemented. The thickness variation is limited to the addition or removal of one ply with respect to the thickness distribution used for the stiffness matching phase. The results of the optimization are summarized in Table 1. The table shows the evolution of the mass and of the mechanical constraints for the 3 SSTs presented in Fig. 6. The first solution minimizes the **A**-distance in Fig. 6 and the third solution minimizes the **D**-distance. All solutions share the same initial mass for the SST-base optimization. It can be seen from Table 1 that the solutions resulting from stiffness matching are infeasible with respect to both the failure constraint and the maximal displacement constraint $0 \leq u_x \leq 9 \text{ mm}$ and $-0.7 \text{ mm} \leq u_y \leq 0$. Nevertheless, feasibility is restored with little if any weight penalty.

In the post processing of the optimization, the thickness distribution is rounded up to an integer number of plies and the final design is translated from PSHELL to PCOMP elements. The values of the failure criteria for the rounded solution are evaluated at ply level with the modified Tsai-Hill failure criterion and shown in Table 1. The distribution of the number of plies and the polar plots of the stiffness $E_{11}(\theta)$ of the final design are shown in Fig. 7. The final mass saving for the shell is about 17 %. Compared to the 24 % mass saving of the first level idealized design, most of the additional mass comes from the ceiling operations to map the continuous thickness distributions to integer ply numbers. Significant margins with respect to both maximal displacement constraints and strength constraints are obtained for all rounded solution which suggests that slightly lower mass could be achieved with a less conservative strategy to map thickness distribution to ply numbers. Starting from the reference solution, 20 FEA analyses only have been used to find the design shown in Fig. 7.

SST-based optimization						Rounded solution		
Initial mass [g]	Point D (u_x, u_y) [mm]	Failure criteria	Final mass [g]	Point D (u_x, u_y) [mm]	Failure criteria	Mass [g]	Point D (u_x, u_y) [mm]	Failure criteria
358	(<u>9.24</u> , -0.66)	<u>1.36</u>	355 g	(8.98, -0.69)	1.00	359 g	(8.66, -0.64)	0.89
358	(<u>9.32</u> , -0.66)	<u>1.19</u>	361 g	(8.86, -0.69)	1.00	362 g	(8.60, -0.66)	0.88
358	(<u>9.48</u> , -0.73)	<u>1.18</u>	362 g	(8.89, -0.69)	1.00	368 g	(8.61, -0.67)	0.86

Table 1: Evolution of the mass and mechanical constraints during the SST-based optimization and its final post-processing. Constraint violating values are underlined.

Figure 7: Distribution of number of plies of the final design and polar plots of the stiffness $E_{11}(\theta)$.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The paper presents an original optimization strategy combining thickness optimization and stacking sequence table optimization within a bi-level optimization framework. The method is applied to the minimization of the mass of an automotive composite wishbone arm. At a first level, a combined thickness and lamination parameters optimization is performed with a fixed subdivision of the structure into 35 design zones. Maximal displacement constraints, strength constraints and lamination parameters feasibility constraints are enforced. The resulting idealized design shows a 24 % mass saving with respect to the reference uniform thickness design. Second level optimization starts with a stiffness matching phase. A specialized evolutionary algorithm is used to match stacking sequence tables to the stiffness distribution of the first level idealized design. A bi-objective optimization is performed that minimizes both the distance in membrane space and the distance in bending space. The stiffness matching phase is inexpensive in terms of computational cost since no structural analysis is required. However, feasibility of the solutions is not guaranteed. Thus, a second optimization phase is required to restore feasibility while minimizing the mass of the designs. This is achieved by parameterizing, through the stacking sequence tables, the relation between the thickness and the stiffness of the shells within a continuous thickness optimization. The resulting thickness distributions are finally rounded up to the nearest integer number of plies to obtain fully defined laminated designs. The lightest solution found at the end of the process shows 17 % mass savings with respect to the reference uniform thickness design. The overall calculation cost is very low.

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REFERENCES

- [1] F.-X. Irisarri, A. Lasseigne, F.-H. Leroy, and R. Le Riche, "Optimal design of laminated composite structures with ply drops using stacking sequence tables," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 107, pp. 559–569, Jan. 2014.
- [2] D. Liu and V. V. Toropov, "A lamination parameter-based strategy for solving an integer-continuous problem arising in composite optimization," *Comput. Struct.*, vol. 128, pp. 170–174, Nov. 2013.
- [3] F.-X. Irisarri, M. M. Abdalla, and Z. Gürdal, "Improved Shepard's Method for the Optimization of Composite Structures," *AIAA J.*, vol. 49, no. 12, pp. 2726–2736, Dec. 2011.
- [4] J. E. Herencia, R. T. Haftka, P. M. Weaver, and M. I. Friswell, "Lay-Up Optimization of Composite Stiffened Panels Using Linear Approximations in Lamination Space," *AIAA J.*, vol. 46, no. 9, pp. 2387–2391, Sep. 2008.
- [5] M. Montemurro, A. Vincenti, and P. Vannucci, "A Two-Level Procedure for the Global Optimum Design of Composite Modular Structures—Application to the Design of an Aircraft Wing: Part 1: Theoretical Formulation," *J. Optim. Theory Appl.*, vol. 155, no. 1, pp. 1–23, Oct. 2012.
- [6] D. Liu, V. V. Toropov, O. M. Querin, and D. C. Barton, "Bilevel Optimization of Blended Composite Wing Panels," *J. Aircr.*, vol. 48, no. 1, pp. 107–118, Jan. 2011.
- [7] M. W. Bloomfield, C. G. Diaconu, and P. M. Weaver, "On feasible regions of lamination parameters for lay-up optimization of laminated composites," *Proc. R. Soc. Math. Phys. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 465, no. 2104, pp. 1123–1143, Apr. 2009.
- [8] P. Vannucci, "A Note on the Elastic and Geometric Bounds for Composite Laminates," *J. Elast.*, vol. 112, no. 2, pp. 199–215, Jul. 2013.
- [9] S. Setoodeh, M. Abdalla, and Z. Gurdal, "Approximate Feasible Regions for Lamination Parameters," 2006.
- [10] Y. Meddaikar, F.-X. Irisarri, and M. M. Abdalla, "Stacking Sequence Optimization of Blended Composites using a Modified Shepard's Method and Stacking Sequence Tables," *Submitt. Struct. Multidiscip. Optim.*

- [11] Z. Gürdal, R. T. Haftka, and P. Hajela, *Design and optimization of laminated composite materials*. New York, NY: Wiley, 1999.
- [12] H. Ghiasi, D. Pasini, and L. Lessard, "Optimum stacking sequence design of composite materials Part I: Constant stiffness design," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 90, no. 1, pp. 1–11, Sep. 2009.
- [13] H. Ghiasi, K. Fayazbakhsh, D. Pasini, and L. Lessard, "Optimum stacking sequence design of composite materials Part II: Variable stiffness design," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 93, no. 1, pp. 1–13, Dec. 2010.
- [14] G. Raju, Z. Wu, and P. Weaver, "On Further Developments of Feasible Region of Lamination Parameters for Symmetric Composite Laminates," 2014.
- [15] S. T. IJsselmuiden, M. M. Abdalla, and Z. Gürdal, "Implementation of Strength-Based Failure Criteria in the Lamination Parameter Design Space," *AIAA J.*, vol. 46, no. 7, pp. 1826–1834, Jul. 2008.
- [16] A. Catapano, B. Desmorat, and P. Vannucci, "Invariant formulation of phenomenological failure criteria for orthotropic sheets and optimisation of their strength," *Math. Methods Appl. Sci.*, vol. 35, no. 15, pp. 1842–1858, Oct. 2012.
- [17] M. M. Abdalla, C. Kassapoglou, and Z. Gürdal, "Formulation of composite laminate robustness constraint in lamination parameters space," in *Proceedings of 50th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC structures, structural dynamics, and materials conference. Palm Springs, California, 2009*.
- [18] A. Exertier and C. Fagiano, "Thermoplastic composite wishbone: the future of automotive composites," *JEC Compos. Mag.*, vol. 82, pp. 40–42, Jul. 2013.
- [19] P. Lapeyronnie, P. Paulmier, C. Julien, C. Fagiano, A. Exertier, and L. Rota, "Behaviour of a thermoplastic composite automotive wishbone under mechanical test cases," presented at the 16th International Conference on Experimental Mechanics, Cambridge, UK, 2014.